

D6.2 Establishment of a project website

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Deliverable Information sheet

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HELIX project has received funding from the European Union's Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS): project num. 101057239

Executive summary

This deliverable explains how HELIX project webpage has been created and all issues that have been taken into consideration. This document summarizes the structure, the content and the functionalities of the website developed in the scope of the project. Also, the data protection measures adopted within the site.

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List of abbreviations

EAC	<i>Environmentally Assisted Cracking</i>
EU	<i>European Union</i>
HE	<i>Hydrogen embrittlement</i>
HSS	<i>High-strength steels</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>

1. Overall principles

According to the work plan, Eurecat is responsible for designing and implementing the official HELIX project website. The registered URL is <https://helix-project.eu/>

The sections hereinafter describe the web platform. **The website will be the anchor for all communication activities related to the project and serve as a central point of entry for all public material**, including the project's basic information, resources and public deliverables. The website will be continuously updated with news, links to other relevant sites, details of published papers, conferences and exhibitions during the project and will remain active during at least 4 years after the project's finalisation.

The website platform follows the corporate visual identity of the project created by Eurecat and approved by partners.

Considering that different authors might update the site, a Content Management System has been adopted, to easily and quickly publish the content. Eurecat proposes to use WordPress, as the Eurecat's Research Communications Office has wide experience with this CMS.

Regarding the website language, all content will be available in English.

It is essential that the website is optimised for browsing on tablets and smart phones, so the website has been developed using a responsive design approach.

2. Website structure

The following information architecture for the HELIX website is proposed in the figure below.

3. Website content

The texts hereinafter are the contents published on the website.

3.1 Homepage

It includes a slider with the project's title ("*Hydrogen embrittlement resistant new steel links solutions for off-shore wind turbines*") and the project's main aim ("*Developing and testing fasteners able to withstand high stresses under harsh environmental conditions*").

The homepage also includes a short description of the project, a space highlighting the innovation carried out in the project, a section with the main objectives and a section mentioning the consortium linking to the consortium page.

Moreover, a section at the homepage showing the latest publications and news has also been created.

The homepage is structured with the following sections:

HELIX project in a nutshell

To increase efficiency and lower production costs, the offshore wind industry is focusing on the development of larger wind generators. The HELIX project aims to provide **high-strength steel fasteners for the offshore wind industry at a lower cost**, more **resistant to corrosion** and with a **wider diameter** to support the ever-increasing size of wind turbines, leading to **higher**

productivity and supporting the development of larger foundations to support above 10MW OWT and allow an easy assembly and disassembly of the whole structure.

During the project, novel high-strength steel grades and protecting zinc-flake based coatings will be developed and validated. In addition, HELIX will use advanced characterisation and traditional techniques under both atmospheric and immersion conditions to **advance in the knowledge of hydrogen absorption in high-strength steels under cathodic protection and in atmospheric conditions.**

BUTTON - Find out more - *Link to HELIX Project page*

A step further in the offshore wind industry

HELIX innovation will advance the state of the art in **coating development** and in **high strength steels with high toughness and resistance to hydrogen embrittlement**. Project results will contribute to better understand the **interaction between steel, coating, and service environment in the hydrogen embrittlement phenomenon.**

Project objectives

- 1- To optimise new lower cost high-strength steel composition with improved hardenability, high toughness, and high hydrogen embrittlement resistance to produce 10.9 and 12.9 steel grades after Quenching and Tempering (Q&T) treatments
- 2- To identify the mechanisms of hydrogen absorption / desorption of the optimised steels
- 3- To develop coatings based on zinc flakes and different topcoat materials to protect the steel and to reduce hydrogen entry in service
- 4- To study the interaction of the optimised steels, the novel coatings and the environment on the hydrogen absorption quantity and mechanisms
- 5- To demonstrate the higher performance of the developed fasteners in real service environments

Consortium

Our team

HELIX interdisciplinary team is made up of **6 partners** from **5 European countries** covering all the value chain, from steel, bolt and fastener manufacturer companies, research centres to universities.

BUTTON - FIND OUT MORE - *Link to Consortium page*

Figure 1. Collage of HELIX partners

From our blog

Project news & Events

In this section, a grid with the latest news of the project is included.

Contact

Do you have a question about our project?

BUTTON - **Contact us** - *Link to Contact page*

3.2 HELIX project

What is HELIX

Advancing in the knowledge of hydrogen absorption in high-strength steels for energy application

The HELIX project aims to provide **lower cost, high corrosion resistant, high strength steel and high diameter fasteners to the offshore wind industry** to support the ever-increasing size of wind turbines, leading to **higher productivity** and supporting the development of larger foundations to support above 10MW OWT, and allow an easy assembly and disassembly of the whole structure.

HELIX will use advanced characterisation and traditional techniques under both atmospheric and immersion conditions to **advance in the knowledge of hydrogen absorption in high strength steels under cathodic protection and in atmospheric conditions.**

This knowledge will not only allow tailoring the steel and coating microstructure to achieve both **excellent corrosion protection ability and low risk of hydrogen embrittlement**, but also **influence on policy and practice in the offshore wind sector.**

HELIX will also identify the **mechanisms of hydrogen absorption/desorption of the optimised steels**, as well as develop **coatings based on zinc flakes** and different topcoat materials to protect the steel and to reduce hydrogen entry in service.

Key data

1. **Start:** July 2022 - **End:** December 2025
2. **Funded under:** Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS-RPJ)

Expected outcomes

Lower cost

Up to 20% reduction

More resistance to corrosion

A minimum of 25 service years

High-strength steel

10.9 and 12.9 grades

High diameter

A minimum size of M64

(Banner)

Increasing steel application competitiveness

Unlocking the full potential of the offshore wind energy

The new [European Green Deal](#) plans to accelerate the use of electricity produced from renewables, developing the full potential of Europe's offshore wind energy.

Offshore wind is set to play a central role and has the potential to become the largest source of electricity supply.

Several types of offshore structures are already used or in development. A great deal of offshore wind projects in Europe are being developed and installed capacity is expected to increase in the next years.

To increase efficiency and lower production costs, the offshore wind industry is focusing on the development of larger wind generators, in which the HELIX project contributes by providing more resistant high-strength steel fasteners.

Key outputs

- **Optimised steel grades**

Optimised steel grades with high hardenability, hydrogen embrittlement resistance and toughness.

- **High dimension fasteners**

Demonstration of the feasibility of high dimension fasteners with lower cost and high performance in real offshore environment.

- **Zinc-flakes-based coatings**

Novel zinc-flakes-based coatings with high corrosion resistance and low to no hydrogen production.

- **Beyond state-of-the-art research**

Advances in the understanding of hydrogen embrittlement in high-strength steels in offshore environments.

- **Material behaviour prediction**

Experimental results to predict the material behaviour in real service life.

- **Industrial guidelines**

Guidelines for the offshore wind industry for the correct protection of fasteners.

What is hydrogen embrittlement?

Hydrogen enters into the material via adsorption through the surface. Once absorbed, it is trapped in different microstructural sites with different activation energy.

Hydrogen located in interstitial sites is called “diffusible hydrogen” and presents the lowest activation energy.

When the material is exposed to external stresses or residual stresses, diffusible hydrogen diffuses to zones of high stress, resulting in hydrogen embrittlement.

3.2.1 Work Plan & Deliverables

Page showing a description of each work package and giving access to the executive summaries to the confidential deliverables and full access to the public ones.

The work is divided into six Work Packages (WP):

WP1. Steel optimisation and manufacturing

Objectives:

- To define steel requirements for offshore fastener applications of metrics and grades equal and over M64 and 10.9 grade.
- To develop a suitable high-strength steel grade 10.9 and 12.9 and its production route.
- To manufacture and provide industrial material for testing.

- *D1.1 Initial characterisation of the two proposed chemical compositions*

WP2. Steel Characterization and Selection

The main objective of this work package is:

- To select the most suitable steel composition more suitable for large size fasteners applied in aggressive environments.

To reach this objective, the following technical objectives will also need to be achieved:

- To characterise the steels obtained in WP1 (chemical composition, mechanical properties and metallography)
- To study the resistance to hydrogen embrittlement of the newly developed steels
- To study the differences of hydrogen trapping sites in each heat-treated steel

- *D2.1 Report on the selection of best performing 10.9 and 12.9 steel grades*
- *D2.2 Identification of hydrogen absorption/desorption mechanisms of the optimized steels and analysis of their hydrogen embrittlement susceptibility under cathodic protection*
- *D2.3 Identification of hydrogen absorption/desorption mechanisms of the optimized steels and analysis of their hydrogen embrittlement susceptibility in atmospheric conditions*

WP3. Coating performance and effects of environment on hydrogen embrittlement

Objectives:

- To develop coatings with expected maximal corrosion protection ability and minimal tendency to induce hydrogen formation on the steel surface and hydrogen embrittlement.
- To prepare series of high-strength steels samples coated with selected combinations of primers and topcoats with expected optimal performance.
- To characterise the coating microstructure and thickness.

- To test the coatings in view of corrosion resistance in simulated marine conditions and seawater exposure.
 - To measure the effect of the coatings on hydrogen entry induced by corrosion processes into steel substrate in model seawater under cathodic protection and in simulated marine atmosphere, both on intact and defected surfaces.
 - To study fundamental links between high-strength steels and coating composition and structure and hydrogen uptake.
 - To assess the effect of corrosion-induced atomic hydrogen on the eventual loss of mechanical properties of coated high-strength steels under constant load and cyclic loading (fatigue corrosion) conditions.
 - To select the optimal type, composition and structure of coating for protection of high-strength steels fasteners based on results of a systematic laboratory study.
 - To better understand the interaction of environment, coating and steel substrate related to hydrogen embrittlement.
- *D3.1 Preparation and characterization of coatings*
 - *D3.2 Corrosion resistance of coated high strength fasteners*
 - *D3.3 Hydrogen embrittlement resistance of coated high strength steels*

WP4. Coating performance and effects of environment on hydrogen embrittlement

The main objectives of this work package are:

- To establish the manufacturing route for M42 and M64 HV-bolts with the new coated high-strength steels (PLUS) grades 10.9 and 12.9 following the standard DAST-021.
 - To manufacture M42 and M64 HV-bolts with 10.9 and 12.9 PLUS steel grades with the new coatings following the standard DAST-021.
 - To manufacture the reference bolts, i.e. hot-dip galvanized M42 and M64 HV-bolts with 10.9 PLUS steel grades following the standard DAST-021.
 - To characterise the manufactured HV-bolts according to DAST-021 and ISO 898-1:2013 and special requirements of wind industry.
 - To characterise the coated assemblies (bolts, nuts and washers) 10.9 in accordance to standard DAST-021.
 - To characterise the coated assemblies 12.9 and to determine the friction coefficient.
- *D4.1 Manufacturing and characterisation of 10.9 and 12.9 PLUS steel grade coated bolts and their assemblies*

WP5. Component Validation in Real Environment

The main objectives of this work package are:

- To define the service conditions to be simulated for evaluation of full-scale components (HV-PLUS 10.9 and 12.9 coated bolts) (atmospheric and immersion zones).
 - To design the adapted test beds for full-scale testing.
 - To expose the systems and define the indicators for in-situ evaluations.
 - To evaluate the performance of full-scale selected systems made in WP4 (e. g. coated bolting) in the defined simulated service conditions (natural seawater).
 - To correlate the full-scale results with the laboratory results obtained in WP2 and WP3.
 - To provide the simulated field results for guidelines.
-
- *D5.1 Corrosion resistance of full-scale components in a real environment (atmospheric)*
 - *D5.2 Corrosion resistance of full-scale components in a real environment (immersion under CP)*
 - *D5.3 Guidelines for the offshore industry*

WP6. Project coordination, dissemination and exploitation

The main objectives of this work package are:

- To coordinate the different work packages, and following up on the project outcomes vs. the plans, as well as with the European Commission.
 - To organise and manage regular opportunities for the partners to meet and discuss (kickoff and periodic project progress meetings) about the content and the progress of the project.
 - To support each partner with their obligations under this project (performance, time, cost) and to guarantee the successful on-time delivery of all project reports and other necessary documents (Technical and Financial reports).
 - To promote project visibility by disseminating the project results to the scientific & industrial community, and to the public.
-
- *D6.1: Comprehensive overview of the project (State of the Art)*
 - *D6.2: Establishment of a project website*
 - *D6.3: Risk Assessment and Contingency plan*
 - *D6.4: Report on Dissemination Activities*
 - *D6.5: Publishable Report*

3.3 Consortium

Section devoted to the partners' corporate information. This page includes a list of the 6 partners integrating HELIX consortium, with a brief description of each organisation and their contribution to the project.

A counter has been included to detail the type of organisations participating in HELIX.

“Our multidisciplinary team is build up of 6 organisations from 4 different European countries: 1 technology center, 1 research institute, 1 university and 3 companies.”

Additionally, each organisation has a button sending to their website, as well as buttons for their social media corporate channels.

Eurecat (coordinator)

Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

Figure 2. Eurecat logo

The centre offers solutions to their innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. It brings together the expertise of 650 professionals who generate a volume of income of 50M€ per year. Serving more than a thousand companies, Eurecat is involved in 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value.

Contribution to the HELIX project

Eurecat is responsible of coordinating the project and the dissemination of project results. With a large experience in hydrogen embrittlement, Eurecat leads the steel characterisation and selection, participating also in the steel optimisation and manufacturing as well as the analysis of coating performance and effects of environment on hydrogen embrittlement.

SIDENOR

Sidenor I+D is the R&D centre of Sidenor Special Steels, one of the European leaders in the fabrication of special steel long products.

Sidenor I+D focuses its activities on the optimization of the steel production process and the development

Figure 3. Sidenor logo

of new steel solutions for sectors such as automotive, energy, etc. The centre, with more than 35 years of experience, combines the knowledge of 52 scientists and engineers and state-of-the-art equipment available in its laboratory.

Contribution to the HELIX project

The role of Sidenor I+D in the HELIX project is focused on the development of the new steels for wind fasteners and their complete metallurgical characterization, including fatigue testing.

Institut de la Corrosion

Institut de la Corrosion, affiliated to RISE (Research Institute Sweden) is the largest research institute in Europe in field of corrosion.

Figure 4. Institut de la Corrosion logo

Institut de la Corrosion (IC) is established in Brest, France is a subsidiary of Research Institute Sweden (RISE) with main office in Gothenburg, Sweden. The core business of IC is corrosion testing, research and development in the field of protection against corrosion. Including both activities in France and Sweden, it is the largest institute in Europe in field of corrosion with a team of over 100 corrosion engineers and technicians.

Contribution to the HELIX project

Institut de la Corrosion is in charge of the evaluation of HE and fatigue testing in real sea water, cyclic corrosion tests according to several standards, and coating testing in simulated offshore conditions. Crucial for the project, Institut de la Corrosion has the possibility to expose the new developments to real environment at the field seawater station in the bay of Brest.

PEINER

PEINER Umformtechnik GmbH (PUT) is a worldwide system supplier. PUT supplies leading manufacturers of wind turbines with quality products for safety-related applications. The product spectrum ranges from HV/HRC and DAST fittings to double ends. PUT is the market leader for HV bolt sets, supplies the steel construction industry with high-strength HV PEINER - bolts and is a full-service provider for HV, HV Pass, HV Black and HRC sets (optionally also with a special coating).

Figure 5. PEINER logo

Further competencies are engineering: PUT is a development partner for the automotive and mechanical engineering industries and supplies high-strength fasteners with cold and hot forming parts with automated, complex machining process and testing.

Contribution to the HELIX project

PEINER is responsible for manufacturing of bolts, nuts and washers for the project. In addition, PEINER will perform the tests such as tensile tests, hardness tests and friction tests.

DÖRKEN

DÖRKEN Coatings unites experts from the fields of high-performance corrosion protection and premium coatings.

With over 1000 employees worldwide and an annual turnover of ca 400M€ we offer solutions for high-quality surface protection, colour systems and pigment pastes since 1892. With our innovative systems we protect diverse components against corrosion. We are convinced that together with our customers and partners we can develop the best solution precisely where it is required. And at the same time make the use of raw materials more sustainable and efficient.

Figure 6. DÖRKEN logo

Contribution to the HELIX project

DÖRKEN is responsible for the development, selection and application of the best possible zinc flake coatings, which are intended to provide corrosion protection on the one hand and to avoid corrosion-related hydrogen embrittlement on the other.

University of Chemistry and Technology in Prague

University of Chemistry and Technology in Prague (UP) is the largest university in Central Europe providing education in all areas of chemistry. Technopark Kralupy is a branch of UP devoted to applied research and industrial projects, helping in linking interests of industry and knowledge available at the university.

Figure 7. University of Chemistry and Technology Prague logo

The Department of Construction Metallic Materials of Technopark Kralupy is focused on atmospheric corrosion, corrosion protection by coatings and accelerated corrosion testing. It provides over 80 expertise and consultancy works a year and participates in numerous national and international projects financed directly by industry or from public resources.

Contribution to the HELIX project

The team of UP applies its broad expertise in interactions of hydrogen with metallic materials. It is studying conditions that may lead to hydrogen entry to coated high strength steel joining elements in order to design advanced coating systems mitigating the risk of hydrogen embrittlement.

3.4 News and events

This section is for publishing any news related to the project. i.e: about meetings, first results, publications, etc. **News articles will be published regularly by Communication and Dissemination Leader Eurecat.** News articles will be categorized in self-explanatory categories to facilitate filtering.

This page will include an agenda announcing events where HELIX is attending / participating (conferences, fairs, congresses and workshops) and a list of articles regarding the events attended, type of dissemination activity, target-profile /audience covered, number of attendees and an overview of the feedback received.

3.5 Contact

This section shows a form for visitors to send comments and questions. The form includes the fields (Name, Surname, Email, Company and Message).

It also includes information about the project coordinator:

GET IN TOUCH!

Project coordinator

Amadeu Concustell

Eurecat Technology Center

info@helix-project.eu

ADDRESS

Eurecat - Manresa

Pl. de la Ciència, 2

08243 Manresa

On the other hand, the email info@helix-project.eu has been created and is shown at the website as another way of contact. The project coordinator and the communication and dissemination manager have access to that email in order to manage all information requests received.

4. Layout

The website menu is available from all pages, allowing visitors to find the information that they are interested in no matter how they arrived on the site.

The overall design and home page of the website includes the following elements:

Header

- HELIX logo to appear in the header.
- Navigation menu.
- Contact information

Footer

- RFCS logo to appear in the footer. Under the logo will appear the phrase *'This project has received funding from the European Union's Research Fund for Coal and Steel programme under grant agreement No. 101057239. This website reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.'*
- Link to legal notice.
- Link to privacy policy.
- Link to cookies policy.
- E-mail
- Copyright.

5. Managing and updating policy

The website has been developed by Eurecat with the inputs received from all partners in the consortium.

The website will be updated from now on by the Communication Leader Eurecat together with the inputs sent by all partners every time a new dissemination action is done, a result is achieved, or there is other news worth publishing.

News worthiness will be established at consortium level. The upload policy for public contractual deliverables will be as follows:

1. As soon as the document has been accepted by the Consortium after the internal peer-reviews, an executive summary will be made available.

2. Once the deliverable is also approved by the European Commission, it will be then made formally public in PDF format provided it is at public dissemination level.

To ensure proper compliance with IPR management procedures agreed amongst consortium partners and described in the Description of Action (DoA)/Grant Agreement, partners aiming to publish in the HELIX webpage are aware that before any disclosure of information the foreseen IPR project fact-sheet should be consulted. If they still have further doubts, the IPR manager may be contacted to avoid confidentiality issues.

6. Analytics

The HELIX website has installed Matomo in the platform's back end to monitoring all the traffic and obtain, periodically, reports about the site's performance. Instead of Google Analytics, Matomo does not compromise data security and privacy, guaranteeing full data ownership and that none of it is ever sent to other services or third parties.

Google Search Console will be used to upload the file robots.txt to make easier for Google Robots the indexation.

7. Site hosting, installation & maintenance

Eurecat has been responsible for setting up the website (domain purchase, hosting and Wordpress.org configuration), as well as creating content and design the fixed sections.

As the Communication leader, Eurecat will be responsible for maintaining the site until the project's end and until two years after and adding content to the website. All pages have been optimised for the search engines (SEO), ensuring that the HELIX website is well positioned in the browsers.

8. Data protection

The HELIX project website is compliant with all European requirements and standards with regards to data protection and observes the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).

The website has been adapted to the latest directives published by the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) on July 2020, which came into force on October 31st, 2020 with the purpose to align the cookies installation with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) consent requirements. The latest version of the AEPD "Guidelines on the Use of Cookies", compared with the previous one, specifies that the consent must be granted by clearly accepting the cookies or carrying out similar actions to click "I accept". In that sense, browsing the website or the use the scroll bar cannot be construed as an affirmative action, nor the use of cookie walls that do not provide an alternative to the consent.

In order to comply with the new AEPD directives, EUT, as the owner of the website www.selfy-project.eu, has installed a cookies banner allowing the user to decide on which non-necessary cookies to install. By complying with the novel regulation, web analytics will only be tracked for users accepting this type of cookies, which may result in losing some statistics on the number of web visits, page viewed or number of users.

The users may revise their cookies' selection at any time as the Cookies Setting Banner is available at the bottom right part of the page. The website also includes specific pages for allocating the privacy policy (<https://helix-project.eu/privacy-policy/>), the cookies policy (<https://helix-project.eu/cookies-policy/>) and the legal notice (<https://helix-project.eu/legal-warning/>).

The webpage includes one form gathering personal data from users to manage user's queries. EUT is the data controller. The data of the contact form will be transferred to partners involved in the project to better reply to the requests.

The website will also include specific forms to manage the registration of interest users to project events. The data included in these forms will be disclosed with the organising partner with the solely objective to register the users to the event and be able, afterwards, to send event materials to attendees.

8.1 Legal notice

By fulfilling the Spanish Information Society Services and Electronic Commerce Act 34/2002 of 11th July (LSSICE), users are hereby informed that the domain owner www.helix-project.eu is FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (hereinafter “**Provider**” or “**Eurecat**”), whose identification data details are as follows:

Registered Office: Avda Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès (BCN)

Tax Identification Code: G66210345

Email address: info@helix-project.eu

Register details: registered at Registre de Fundacions de la Generalitat de Catalunya with number 2826

SUBJECT MATTER AND SCOPE

The main purpose of the Legal Notice is to provide the information regarding access and uses to the web www.helix-project.eu (hereinafter “**Web**”) which has the subject matter of informing about the HELIX project as well as to allows to the Internet users access thereto.

By accessing and/or using the Web, are considered to hold the role of a user (hereinafter “**Users**”) an in consequence the acceptance with no reservations of each and whole parts of its Legal Notice, Privacy and Cookies policies or, any other terms and conditions linked to the Web.

Users must carefully read the Legal Notice, the Privacy and Cookies Policy, also to consulting its content often to stay tuned about it because of the Eurecat's right to carry out improves or updates at the Web contents or services, without prior notice being necessary. The Users who do not accept the content of its Legal Notices, Privacy or Cookies Policy or any related terms and conditions related to the Web, Eurecat begs you to not access neither to use the Web.

TERMS OF USE

Users are the sole responsible for the use they could make of the Web as for the content reproduce out or through the Web and for the damages that it may cause. The Provider shall not be held liable for any damage from the Users Web access and uses. Users shall be held

liable for any damages that the Provider could be caused as a result of a breach of the obligations undertaken by virtue of this Legal Notice, the Privacy and Cookies Policy and the applicable regulations.

Users undertake to carefully use the whole Web, its contents and services, fulfilling with the applicable regulations, the rules of moral generally accepted, good conduct and public order as well as this Legal Notice and any other legal conditions or obligations included on the Web.

Users undertake to refrain the Web use, the contents and services thereto, for illegal or prohibited purposes, that could harm rights and interests of third parties or infringe this Legal Notice, as well as any actions that could damage, disable, overload, harm or hinder the normal use of the Web and its contents and services to other users.

Moreover, User expressly undertakes to do not delete, manipulate, disturb disable or from any other way damage the data, software and hardware, technical resources, electronic documents on the Web, as not to hinder access by other users to the Web by massive use of he Web resources, within those Eurecat provide the Web services and contents, and any other actions could damage, interrupt or leading errors on the Web.

Likewise, Users undertake not to introduce programs, viruses, macros applets, controllers ActiveX or any other logical or sequential characters devices that may cause any kind of alteration on the Provider or third parties' systems.

Users agrees that the documents, graphics published on the Web server may include technical incorrections or typographic errors, as well as the Provider or its services suppliers, may develop Web improvements and/or changes at any time without it entitled the User to claim for damages.

In the same way, Users agrees that Eurecat reserves' the right at any time to modify or interrupt the Web, conforming to "Modifications and Interruptions", as well as the right to disable, limited or blocked Web access that infringes the Legal Notice, the third party's rights, the applicable laws and/or public order, without it entitled the User to claim for damages against the Provider.

INTELLECTUAL OR INDUSTRIAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

The Provider or its licensors are the holders of all the intellectual or industrial property rights related to the Web and the contents thereto, this being deemed to mean, in particular but not limited to, the designs, data bases, underlying programs (includes source an object codes), as well as different elements included on the Web (texts, logos, graphics, photographs, colors...), structure, order and the legal texts, etcetera (hereinafter "**Contents**"). The trademarks and trade names (hereinafter "**Distinctive Signs**") are owned by the Provider or its licensors.

The use of the Web does not grant to the User related intellectual and/or industrial property rights licenses. Likewise, reproducing, copying, distributing, putting available to third parties or making public communications, transforming or modifying the Contents and/or the Distinctive Signs, by the User is prohibited unless express consent to do so has given from who concern or are lawful actions.

MODIFICATIONS AND INTERRUPTIONS

Access to the Web and its contents and services thereto, may be interrupted due to maintenance tasks or failures beyond the Provider which may be solved by the period required.

Eurecat hereby reserves the right to making modifications at any time without User notifications related to the Web, contents, services, scope, and any information or resources thereto.

Likewise, Provider reserves the right to disable or blocked the Web access or delete or limited the contents in case that considers that infringes this Legal Notice, third parties' rights, the applicable laws and/or the public order.

Provider is not liable about the security mistakes also to the damages that may cause at Users devices (hardware and software) and for the files or documents therein storage, as a consequence of the viruses, Internet or telephone companies' failures, interferences, disconnects or omissions from the operative functions of the Web and/or because of reasons that not belongs to Eurecat.

Provider is not liable from the direct or indirect damages because of Web use, from the server and its modifications and/or interruptions that may be caused to the User or third parties'.

LINKS POLICY (LINKING WEB AND LINKED WEB)

1. Linking Web

Thirds parties whom intent to include link to this Web (hereinafter "**Linking Web**") must fulfil the laws in force and may not host inappropriate, illegal pornographic, violent... content.

Under no circumstances whatsoever shall the Provides be held liable for the contents from Linking Web nor does promote, guarantee, monitor or recommends the contents thereof.

If the Linking Website does not comply with any of the aforementioned terms, this Legal Notice and/or the law, it must be immediately deleted.

1. Linked Web

This Web may include links to webs that belongs to third parties (hereinafter "**Linked Web**") which are allowed to User's access. However, the Provider shall not be held responsible for the contents from Linked Web, instead Users will be the responsible for accepting and checking it the access time by time.

The Linked Web and its respective links do not imply Provider approval, support, or the existence of any marketing or business relationship between the Provider and the third parties located on Linked Web.

SOCIAL MEDIA

Provider may have social media profiles in several social media networks, which accessible to the Users though the links included on the Web, as well as join directly through the social media platform.

The social media networks have their own terms and conditions of use and its privacy policies, for this reason, Users who follows the Provider profile on a social media, shall be under the legal terms stablished therein, as a consequence of that, Provider shall not be liable for any Users damages.

In accordance with the aforementioned, the User data belongs to the social media network, except for those cases that the data has been collected within marketing actions (contest, lottery, promotion...) promoted by the Provider.

The Provider may delete Users comments on their own social media profile in case that considers that infringes this Legal Notice, third parties' rights, the applicable laws and/or public order. In addition, Provider shall be held from liability because of the inappropriate use on its social media profiles by the User as well as the publications that diminish third parties' rights, against applicable regulations, public order or for made a profit from Provider social media networks contents and quotes.

Hereby the links to the privacy policies from the social networks on which the Provider may have an active profile:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/es/privacy>

Facebook: <https://ca-es.facebook.com/privacy/explanation>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/intl/es/yt/about/policies/#community-guidelines>

LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/legal/privacy-policy?_l=es_ES

APPLICABLE LAW

This Legal Notice, legal text and Web shall be governed and interpreted according to Spanish law.

Any disputes that may arise because of the Web use shall be submitted to the relevant Courts and Tribunals in accordance with the consumers regulations applicable.

CONTACT

User may query or comment regarding the Legal Notice or any other matter related to the Web as well as contact to the Provider, though this email address info@helix-project.eu

8.2 Cookies policy

WHAT ARE COOKIES AND WHY DO WE USE THEM ON THE WEBSITE?

A cookie is a file that is downloaded to the user's device when they access certain websites which stores and retrieves information about the browsing activity on their computer.

Cookies allow this website, among other things, to store and retrieve information about the user's decisions and habits. The cookies that exist on this website are necessary for it to function. It is important to highlight that the use of cookies does not provide access to the user's personal data.

WHAT TYPE OF COOKIES EXIST?

Depending on the time they remain active, Cookies can be divided into session or persistent cookies.

- **Session cookies** are designed to collect and store data while the user accesses a website and are removed as soon the explorer is closed. They are normally used to

store information that only needs to be kept in order to provide the service requested by the user on just one occasion.

- **Persistent cookies** remain stored on the device and can be accessed and handled during a period specified by the user of the cookie, which may be from a few minutes to several years.

Additionally, depending on the organisation managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

- **First-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain managed by the website publisher and are used to provide the service requested by the user.
- **Third-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain that is not managed by the website publisher, but by another organisation that handles data obtained from the cookies. Additionally, depending on the organisation managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

In terms of their purpose, the types of cookies are:

- **Technical cookies:** Technical cookies allow the user to browse a website, platform or application and use the different service options found there.
- **Profiling cookies:** Profiling cookies allow the user to access the service with some predefined general features based on a series of criteria on the user's device such as language, settings, etc.
- **Analytical cookies:** Analytical cookies allow the website owner to track and analyse user behaviour on the websites to which they are linked. The information collected is used to measure activity on the websites and to create users' browsing profiles, with the aim of introducing improvements.
- **Advertising cookies:** Advertising cookies allow the advertising spaces that the publisher puts on the website to be managed as efficiently as possible.

WHAT TYPE OF COOKIES DOES THE WEBSITE USE?

The user may consult and set up the website cookies managed by the website publisher at Cookie settings.

The user should take into account that although the cookies may be set up, certain cookies are needed and must be installed to ensure the proper access and use of the website, these cookies do not require the user's agreement or its management.

COOKIE	TYPE	DURATION	DESCRIPTION
cookieLawInfo-checkbox-analytics	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookie is used to store the user consent for the cookies

COOKIE	TYPE	DURATION	DESCRIPTION
			in the category “Analytics”.
cookielawinfo-checkbox-functional	0	11 months	The cookie is set by GDPR cookie consent to record the user consent for the cookies in the category “Functional”.
cookielawinfo-checkbox-necessary	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookies is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category “Necessary”.
cookielawinfo-checkbox-others	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookie is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category “Other.
cookielawinfo-checkbox-performance	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookie is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category “Performance”.
viewed_cookie_policy	0	11 months	The cookie is set by the GDPR Cookie Consent plugin and is used to store whether or not user has consented to the use of cookies. It does not store any personal data.

HOW DO YOU DISABLE COOKIES IN A BROWSER?

The user can adjust the settings in their browser so as not to accept the use of cookies, in which case the user would not have a customized browsing experience. Choosing this setting may result in certain parts of the website not being accessible, as this may cause less effective browsing.

Most browsers currently allow the user to choose whether they want to accept cookies and which types. These settings are usually found in the “settings” or “preferences” in your browser’s menu.

Depending on the browser used by the user and its functionalities used may suppose the installation of cookies that are considered Third-party cookies. For example, if the user chooses Google’s browser and uses its option of translating full website, Google installs cookies in the user’s computers that are not managed by the website publisher. The settings of the browser cookies should be done by the user directly at the browser website.

- These are the instructions to change the cookie settings in the main browsers:
- Information about cookies for [Mozilla Firefox](#).
- Information about cookies for [Internet Explorer](#)
- Information about cookies for [Opera](#).
- Information about cookies for [Google Chrome](#).
- Information about cookies for [Safari](#)

8.3 Privacy policy

Who is the Data Controller of your personal data?

Data Controller: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (“Eurecat” or “Data Controller”)

Tax Identification Code: G-66210345

Address: Avda. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès, Barcelona (Spain)

Email address: legal@eurecat.org

Telephone: +34 93 238 14 00

Data Protections Officer’s email address: dpo@eurecat.org

What are the purposes and the legal basis for the processing of your personal data?

The Data Controller shall process your identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address...) as the data included at your query, given through the contact form, for the purpose to manage and answer the user contact. The legal basis for its data processing is to develop the proper actions to answer the user’s contact (art 6.1 b) GDPR).

The Data Controller, as a member of a consortium, may process your identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address...) as well as other data given by the web forms, for the purpose of give access to it to the other consortium partners, you may consult detailed partner consortium list at [Consortium](#), in those cases that it should be strictly necessary to manage properly the web form purposes. The legal basis for its data processing is the legitimate interest as well as the proper actions to execute the data purposes (art 6.1 b) and f) GDPR). You may obtain further information regarding the recipients of your data consulting the Privacy Policy section “*Who are the recipients of your data?*”.

The Data Controller shall process and have access to user’s navigation data (IP, location, browser...) because of the cookies installed. The mandatory cookies are for to provide the

proper web services, and the accessory cookies are to improve the web services, further information regarding cookies data processing's, consulting the Cookies Policy. The legal basis for data processing related to the mandatory cookies is the legitimate interest (art 6.1 f) GDPR) and the legal basis for the data processing related to accessory cookies is the consent granted by the user (art 6.1 a) GDPR).

Who are the recipients of your data?

Eurecat is the main recipient of user data, however, it may be accessible to third parties that develop services to the Data Controller. Those scenarios that required Eurecat service suppliers' access to the user's data, because of the services arranged, shall be submitted to the legal obligations, which are those of article 28 GDPR'S. In any event, Eurecat service suppliers shall not process the user's data for their own or different purposes and shall not overreach from the services purposes, and, in any case, shall not rent, sold, or make it available to third parties.

The Data Controller shall not transfer your data to third parties without your prior consent, which should fulfill the legal requirements.

The Data Controller in case of legal obligations may transfer your data to third parties, without the user prior consent.

The personal data obtained by the web forms may be transferred to certain consortium partners with whom Eurecat cooperate, for the purpose to manage and answer the user contact as well as to execute the proper actions to carry out the web form purposes for which the data was given This data access by the consortium partners, does not entail a data assignment for its own purposes. You may consult the detailed list of the project consortium partner [here](#).

How long your data shall be kept?

Eurecat shall process your data as long as it is necessary for the purposes of the processing for which the data were given, for fulfill with legal obligations and, in any case, until you ask its deletion.

Even if the User asks the erasure of its data, the Data Controller shall keep them blocked for the term required to afford legal obligations or make them available to third parties who get the proper capacities to assume the certain legal obligations.

Is your data subject to international data transfers?

Your data shall not be subjected to international data transfer, it means outside the European Economic Area ("EEA"). However, Eurecat may have services suppliers located or whom develop its services out of the EEA, in these sense, the Data Controller shall ensure to the User that their data object to international transfers shall be protected with the legal measures, that may consist on standard contractual clauses or privacy certifications, bot legal measures approved by the European Union.

Is your data subjected to profiling or automated decisions?

Your data shall not be subjected to automated decisions neither to profiling because of Eurecat's data processing's.

Eurecat through the accessory cookies installed and agreed by the user, may process user's navigation data to profiling for the purposes of improve the Web services and contents, to obtain navigation and Web statistics, to develop and implement Web improvements. The cookies profiling is subjected to the cookies installed which are strictly linked to the user consent. You may consult further cookies information consulting the Cookies Policy.

What are your personal data rights?

Current privacy laws granted several rights to the users regarding the processing of their data, main information about them is detailed herein:

1. ***Right of access:*** users are entitled to find out which of your personal data are processed and the processing purposes
2. ***Right of rectification:*** users are entitled to request the rectifications regarding their data at any time
3. ***Right of erasure:*** users are entitled to request, at any time, that their data shall be erased from the data controller storage. However, as set out in the above section related on data storage, in certain circumstances to compliance with the laws in force may prevent this right from being exercised
4. ***Right to object:*** users are entitled to object to their personal data from being processed in relation to any of each purposes processing's, pursuant to the privacy policies that may apply in each case.
5. ***Right to restriction of processing:*** users are entitled to request the restriction of purposes processing's in the following cases:
 1. If considers that their data are incorrect or inexact;
 2. If considers that their data has been processing with not the proper legal basis and considered to restrict the processing's instead of requests its erasures;
 3. If the data recorded are no longer required for the processing purposes which were collected for but need its storage to file a lawful claim;
 4. If the user having exercised its right to object for a specific purpose, is awaiting a reply from the data controller to this regard
6. ***Right to data portability:*** user is entitled to request that their personal data that were submitted to the data controller are being disclosed to another data controller, only in case that its request is technically possible and reasonable to do so.

How may you exercise your data rights?

Notwithstanding that your data has been collected within your consent or the proper legal basis, you may object to the data processing at any time whereby without consequences for you, however, depending on the right exercised certain services shall not be able to be rendered.

The users may exercise their rights according to the law terms and conditions by addressing to Eurecat through either of the following:

- (i). by email address to legal@eurecat.org
- (ii). by postal to Parc Tecnològic del Vallès. Avda. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès (BCN)

The user may have the right to contact to the Data Controller Data Protection Officer by email to dpo@eurecat.org

The users if considers that their data shall not been processed with legal basis or its requests or rights shall not been attended properly by the Data Controller, are entitled to file a claim upon the Supervisory Authority competent on data protection matters, it is the Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (www.aepd.es).

8.4 Data treatment information

DATA TREATMENT INFORMATION -CONTACT FORM

Data Controller: The Data Controller is Fundació Eurecat, with Vat number G-66210345 sited at Av. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290, Cerdanyola del Vallès (BCN), legal@eurecat.org (the “Data Controller”)

Data Protection Officer contact information de contact dpo@eurecat.org

Purposes of the data treatment: identifying data (name, surname, email address) and the data and information provided at the form shall be processed to manage and answer your query.

Legal Basis: the legal basis for its data processing are the proper actions to answer and manage your contact (GDPR art 6.1 b).

Recipients: The data shall not be ceded to third parties, although, certain data may be shared to the consortium partners in those cases that it should be required to manage properly your query. However, the data may be accessible to third parties as to the Data Controller services providers or, because of legal obligations. Further information at Privacy Policy.

Storage: The data shall be stored for the term required to develop the purpose of the data processing’s, or, until the data subject request its deletion.

Automated decisions and profiling: the data shall not be object of profiling neither automated decision.

Rights: the consent may be revoked at any time. You may also have the right to access, rectify, erase the data and exercise your right to restriction of the processing data and to ask for the portability of the data according to the legal conditions contacting the data controller at: Fundació Eurecat a Av. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona), or by email a legal@eurecat.org

Supervisory Authority: in case the user shall not obtained the execution of a right petition, or considered it unsatisfactory, or require further information about the subject’s data rights, you may consult to the Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (www.agpd.es).

Further Information: you may consult further information about the data treatment at Privacy Policy.